
Bilthoven, 20 March 2026

The table attached to this document specifies the features of the *Salmonella* and *Shigella* reference strains available at the EURL-PH-FWDB for the Network Laboratories.

The strains are provided as pure cultures in agar, prepared as fresh passages of the reference strains, checked for the specified features during preparation. The stab-agar cultures can be stored at room temperature and are stable for up to six weeks since the date of preparation, reported in each certificate provided together with the reference materials. The strains must be cultured before that date to prepare passages that will be stored frozen after the addition of cryo-preserved.

A certificate will be provided together with the reference materials.

Please note that the reference strains are provided for being used as positive controls in methods set up, for quality assurance purposes, and specific assays (e.g. determination of the serogroup, presence of virulence genes). Any other use or their distribution to other laboratories is not allowed without prior consent from the EURL-PH-FWDB.

BIOSAFETY WARNING

Salmonella and *Shigella* are human pathogens that can cause severe disease. Laboratory acquired infections have been reported. Therefore, please handle any reference materials distributed by the EURL-PH-FWDB according to the national biosafety procedures for pathogenic strains.

Annex 1. List of Salmonella and Shigella reference strains available at the EURL-PH-FWDB

Species	subspecies	Serovar [Mandatory field]
<i>S. enterica</i>	<i>enterica</i>	>250 serovars available
<i>S. enterica</i>	<i>salamae</i>	Please request
<i>S. enterica</i>	<i>arizonae</i>	Please request
<i>S. enterica</i>	<i>diarizonae</i>	Please request
<i>S. enterica</i>	<i>houtenae</i>	Please request
<i>S. enterica</i>	<i>indica</i>	Please request
<i>S. bongori</i>		Please request

Optional: additional requested markers (e.g. MLST, AMR markers)

Species	Serotype [Mandatory field]
<i>Shigella sonnei</i>	Please request
<i>Shigella flexneri</i>	Please request
<i>Shigella boydii</i>	Please request
<i>Shigella dysenteriae</i>	Please request

Optional: additional requested markers (e.g. MLST, AMR markers)